

IMPROVEMENT OF STEEL CLEANLINESS IN TUNDISH OPERATIONS: PHYSICAL MODELING, NUMERICAL SIMULATION AND INDUSTRIAL SCALE VALIDATION

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ABSTRACT

Internal design of a three strand, delta shaped bloom casting tundish has been modified on the basis of water modelling experiments, supported by full-scale numerical simulations. By introducing a pouring box, a twin-slotted dam and a basal wedge in the model tundish, it is shown that proportion of dispersed plug volume (DPV) could be increased nearly two folds in comparison to that of the original tundish design. This, coupled with upwardly directed melt flow from the pouring box, is expected to improve inclusion removal from the tundish. To demonstrate the model investigation further, existing tundish design in a special steel plant was appropriately modified and casting trials carried out. EDS (Energy Dispersive x-ray Spectroscopy) of solidified bloom samples obtained from original and modified design tundish practices confirmed improved cleanliness (in terms of size and volume fraction of inclusions) and demonstrating essentially that higher dispersed plug flow volume, coupled with upwardly directed flow enhance inclusion floatation in steelmaking tundish systems. The present study has also indicated that argon injection in ladle shroud at moderate rate may further aid inclusion removal from tundish.

1. INTRODUCTION

In clean steel production, tundish metallurgy over the years, has assumed considerable importance. It is rather well known that tundish geometry and associated furniture, throughput rate and operating practices largely govern interactions among slag-metal-refractory and gas (typically air) and influence metallurgical performance of steelmaking tundish system. In such context, floatation and removal of inclusions from tundish is of considerable importance to steelmakers since castability and final product quality are intricately related to melt cleanliness. Since direct measurements in high temperature steel processing units are cumbersome and difficult, consequently, many physical and mathematical modelling studies^{1,2)} have been carried out to investigate inclusion removal from steelmaking tundish systems. Inferences on inclusion removal have, in general, been made from two different stand points namely, population balance and residence time distributions. While population balance model directly provides inclusion population density as well as floatation efficiency in terms of numbers³⁾, any increase in dispersed plug flow volume (reflected from RTD calculations/measurements), is taken as a necessary indication of improved inclusion floatation as well as product cleanliness⁴⁾.

Population balance models are sufficiently predictive as direct validation of model results against industrial scale measurements³⁾ have indicated. In contrast, RTD calculations /measurements and corresponding estimates of volume fractions are only indicative and cannot be quantitatively correlated with inclusion population density or inclusion removal efficiency. Despite such, it has been generally acknowledged that relatively high dispersed plug flow volume in presence of surface directed flows is conducive to inclusion floatation and facilitates inclusion removal from steelmaking tundish. Direct validation of such assertions with plant scale data however, has not been possible till date.

Consequently, the primary objective of the present study is to directly correlate residence time distributions calculations with inclusion removal from steelmaking tundish system and to this end, water modelling, full-scale numerical simulation and industrial scale measurements have been applied. As a case study, processing of steel in a three strand, eleven tonne, bloom casting tundish has been considered.

Table 1 Model tundish and operating parameters *vis a vis* those in the full scale tundish system.

The 0.5 scale water model tundish system	Parameters	0.5 scale water model	The bloom casting tundish
	Operating parameters		
	Mass flow rate (kg/s)	0.366	13.5
	Tundish frontal length at base(mm)	1600	3200
	Maximum tundish width at base (mm)	790	1580
	Melt depth (mm)	350	700
	Inlet diameter (mm)	25	50
	Outlet diameter (mm)	7	30
	Volumetric argon injection rate, m ³ /s	-----	1.33x10 ⁻⁴ - 1.7x10 ⁻⁴
	Values considered in physical and mathematical simulations		
	Working fluid	water	steel
	Density(kg/m ³)	998	7200
	Dynamic viscosity (mPa)	0.001003	0.0077
	Temperature (K)	298	1840-1870
	Tracer amount (kg)	0.15	7.5

2. PRESENT WORK

2.1 The Bloom Casting Tundish, Operating Parameters and Physical Modelling

The three-strand, bloom casting tundish has a delta shape and was operated originally with only a rectangular shaped pouring box, without any flow modifiers. To investigate flow, RTD and inclusion removal efficiency, a 0.5 scale, PERSPEX model of the tundish was fabricated in our laboratory and

operated with water at appropriately scaled flow rate deduced on the basis of Froude similarity criterion⁵). Principal operating parameters and key dimensions of the model *via a vis* the full scale are summarised in Table 1. Extensive flow visualization and RTD measurements were carried out in the water model tundish and to these ends, popular and well established experimental methods (viz., high speed photography and electrical conductivity etc.) were applied.

Figure 1 Typical RTD or “C” curve for a single strand tundish and nomenclature.

Pulse addition of a tracer (typically an electrolyte) into ladle shroud produces an electrical response at tundish outlet analogous to the one shown in Fig.1. This, in the literature, is typically referred to as RTD or “C” curve. On the basis of such⁶), key residence time distribution (RTD) parameters such as, (i) the minimum breakthrough time, t_{min} (normalized as θ_{min}), when the tracer is first detected at the outlet, (ii) time to attain peak tracer concentration, t_{peak} (or, θ_{peak}) and (iii) the mean residence time, t_{av} (or, θ_{av}) are estimated. Normalized or dimensionless mean residence time is estimated from “C” curve as:

$$\theta_{av} = \frac{1}{\tau} \frac{\int_0^{2\tau} C t dt}{\int_0^{2\tau} C dt} \quad (1)$$

in which, τ is the nominal residence time ($= V/Q$; V is the tundish volume and Q is the total in-flow rate), C is instantaneous concentration and t is time. On the basis of RTD parameters, dead and dispersed volume fractions can be readily estimated from⁶):

$$V_{dead} = 1 - \frac{Q_a}{Q} \theta_{av} \quad (2)$$

and

$$V_{dp} = \frac{\theta_{min} + \theta_{peak}}{2} \quad (3)$$

It is to be noted here, Q_a/Q appearing in Eq.(2), represents the area under the curve between the limit $t=0$ and $t= 2\tau$. Finally, mixed volume fraction (V_{mix}) is estimated from the balance once dead and dispersed plug flow volume fractions are calculated via Eq.(2 and (3) respectively. From strand specific “C” Curves (e.g., Fig.1), an overall “C” curve for the three-strand tundish can be readily deduced following the procedure outlined in ref.1.

Preliminary flow visualization and tracer ($KMnO_4$ solution) dispersion studies have indicated that the delta shaped tundish is relatively sluggish and is associated with pronounced dead flow regions, particularly in the bottom region, far away from shroud entry point. To improve tundish hydrodynamic performance, different types of flow modifiers have been explored in this study. Various options considered included:

- a flat basal wedge with wells,
- an embedded pouring box,
- an inclined basal wedge and
- a dam with twin, directional slots.

These modifiers were employed individually as well as in-conjunction, to assess their overall impact on residence time distributions (RTD). Schematics of the tundish fitted with different types of flow modifiers are shown in Fig.2.

Figure 2 Inlaid floor configurations of the three strand bloom casting tundish. (I) Original tundish design (II) Tundish with a raised bottom and three wells (III) Tundish with an inclined basal wedge (IV) Tundish with an inclined basal wedge and a twin-slotted dam.

Residence time distribution parameters obtained from water model investigation, for all four design configurations (Case I through Case IV, Fig.2) are summarised in Table 2. These indicate that configuration IV, i.e., tundish operated with a slotted dam and a basal, inclined wedge leads to highest dispersed plug flow volume in the system. As the pouring box produces surface directed flows (see later), consequently, it is reasonable to assume that a relatively high dispersed plug flow volume, in presence of an upwardly directed flow can facilitate inclusion removal leading to improved melt

cleanliness⁴). The validity of such assertion was evaluated systematically, through numerical simulations as well as industrial scale trials, as discussed in the following.

Table 2 Overall RTD characteristics and the associated volume fractions in the water model and their comparison with numerical predictions. (a) Residence time characteristics and (b) Associated flow volume fractions.

(a) Residence time characteristics

Case	Experiments				Numerical simulation			
	Time, s		Residence time, s	Nominal residence time, s	Time, s		Residence time, s	Nominal residence time, s ¹
	Min	Peak			Min	Peak		
I	34	77.5	546.0	806.9	42.5	63.5	578.4	806.0
II	38	79	423.3	702.9	33.5	59.5	534.5	715.8
III	41.5	71.5	558.9	725.9	35.5	64	562.4	762.2
IV	39.5	98.5	381.2	725.9	38.5	251	591.2	759.5

(b) Flow volume fractions

Case	Experimental volume fractions			Numerically predicted volume fractions		
	dead	dispersed plug	mixed	dead	dispersed plug	Mixed
I	0.323	0.069	0.608	0.282	0.060	0.657
II	0.409	0.082	0.510	0.253	0.065	0.682
III	0.267	0.074	0.659	0.262	0.065	0.673
IV	0.498	0.091	0.411	0.222	0.191	0.588

2.2. Mathematical Modelling

Many prior studies¹ have demonstrated that hydrodynamics and tracer dispersion phenomena in steel making tundish systems can be predicted with reasonable certainty through a steady-state, turbulent flow calculation procedure. Accordingly, RANS (Reynolds Average Navier-Stokes) equations in conjunction with a scalar transport model have been applied to simulate flow and RTD phenomena in the tundish, embodying the standard, $k-\varepsilon$ turbulence model⁷). Governing equations and associated boundary conditions applicable to steady state tundish operations are well known and available elsewhere^{1,8}). These are consequently, not re-iterated here. All computations reported in this study were carried out via the commercial CFD solver, ANSYS Fluent™ 18.0. In order to optimize trade-off between solution precision and CPU time, the computational, full-scale domain was discretized into approximately 200,000 tetrahedral cells. A sufficiently stringent convergence criterion, $= 5 \times 10^{-4}$, was set on all variables. Taking advantage of geometrical symmetry, only half the tundish domain was considered for all numerical simulations reported in this work. This allowed deployment of large number mesh elements, needed for greater accuracy, which was found to be particularly advantageous during full-scale simulations (see later).

¹ Simulated tundish volume was marginally different from the actual due to various approximations in geometry building. Accordingly, as seen, experimental and numerical nominal residence times are marginally different. Numerical flow volumes presented in Table 2(b) have been estimated based on theoretically predicted C curve embodying the numerical nominal residence time.

Numerically predicted flow patterns in the modified design, water model tundish (Case IV) are shown in Fig.3. These are suggestive of strong flow recirculation inside the pouring box and substantial, upwardly directed fluid motion in the bulk of liquid, as one would normally anticipate. Corresponding, numerically computed residence time distribution parameters for four different tundish designs are presented in Table 2, along with experimental measurements. Reasonable agreement between the two is readily apparent. Given such, it is reasonable to assume that the turbulent fluid flow and tracer dispersion model developed in this study is sufficiently predictive and replicates water modelling results reasonably accurately.

Figure 3 Velocity vectors in the modified design water model tundish (Case IV). (a) along the transverse vertical plane, passing through the inlet and (b) along the longitudinal vertical plane passing through all the outlets.

Appropriate mesh refinement is a pre-requisite to full-scale computations, if flow and turbulence (these determine RTD) are to be predicted with certainty in a large computational domain. Furthermore, relatively large values of density and viscosity in full-scale computation result in higher absolute value of residuals and errors and to counter this, stricter convergence criteria, $< 5 \times 10^{-5}$ or so is warranted. Increased domain volume (i.e., nearly eight fold w.r.t model tundish), fixed element size and stringent convergence criteria parallelly lead to significant increase in computational time. Numerical computations, as pointed out already, were therefore restricted to half tundish domain to reduce computational time and ensure increased accuracy of prediction. This is justified since flow geometry exhibits symmetry about a transverse, vertical plane, passing through the shroud and the central strand. The final ‘half tundish’ domain was discretized predominantly into three dimensional tetrahedral meshes having approximately 400,000 - 450,000 elements.

Predicted steady state flow on a longitudinal vertical plane of the industrial scale tundish (passing through the three outlets) is shown in Fig.4(a). Equivalent results for the half tundish domain are presented in Fig.4(c). Perfect symmetry in the two set of results is at once evident. Accordingly, corresponding $C \sim t$ curves at two different outlets, overlap with each other as shown in Fig.5. Therefore, all subsequent numerical simulations, reported in this work, were restricted to ‘half-tundish’ geometry and results obtained therefrom were scaled up to draw necessary inferences on the metallurgical performance of the tundish system.

Figure 4 Predicted velocity field in the original, industrial, bloom casting tundish design (Case I; Fig.2) considering (a) full tundish geometry and (b),(c) half tundish geometry.

Figure 5 Predicted variation of tracer concentration at two different tundish outlets of the industrial bloom casting tundish (Case I, Fig.2) considering full and half tundish geometries respectively.

Numerically predicted C curves for two different designs (Cases I and IV; Fig.2) of the industrial bloom casting tundish system is shown in Fig.6. These clearly reveal the influence flow modifiers exert on fluid flow and RTD phenomena in the system. The tendency of short circuiting flows is entirely absent in the modified tundish geometry and as a result, corresponding C curve (i.e., for Case IV) appears to be relatively more diffused. Estimated flow volumes, derived from respective C curves, summarised in Table 3 clearly indicate that proportion of dispersed plug volume in the modified tundish design is increased at the expense of dead volume. Such trends, as one would note here, corroborate strongly water modelling results (see table 2), indicating essentially that incorporation of

an inclined wedge, pouring box and a slotted dam in the industrial tundish, is expected to be beneficial as far as floatation of inclusions and their removal is concerned.

Figure 6 Predicted C curves illustrating a comparison between the two different designs (Cases I and Case IV) of the industrial bloom casting tundish system.

Figure 7 Half tundish simulation results on flows in the modified design, industrial bloom casting tundish system. Flow on a (a) transverse, vertical plane passing through the inlet and the central strand and (b) longitudinal, vertical plane passing through the outlets.

Predicted melt flow on two different planes of the modified design, industrial scale tundish (case IV) is shown in Fig.7. These are on line with equivalent, reduced scale model results (see Fig.3) and confirm substantial, upwardly directed flow in the tundish. Furthermore, a comparison between Figs. 4 and 7 indicates that while relatively large recirculation loops exist in the original tundish (Case I), these are absent and replaced by smaller fluid loops in the modified tundish design (Case IV). The dam, ahead of the shroud helps break the large fluid circulation loops improving dispersed plug flow volume in the system, as has been reflected from results presented in Table 3. Given such, improved metallurgical performance from the modified tundish design can be anticipated.

Table 3 Predicted RTD parameters and residence times for two different designs (Case I and Case IV) of the industrial scale, bloom casting tundish.

Case	Time, s		Residence time, s		Dimensionless times			Volume fractions		
	Min	Peak	Average	Nominal	Min	Peak	Average	Dead	Dispersed	Mixed
I	64	102	964.31	1363.64	0.046	0.075	0.707	0.33	0.061	0.609
IV	57	229	935.14	1295.24	0.044	0.177	0.729	0.282	0.11	0.608

Results and discussion presented so far have been based on a steady state, homogeneous turbulent flow model. In reality, argon is present in ladle shroud (Table 1) and as a result, a two-phase, gas-liquid flow is to be expected in shroud as well as in tundish (particularly in the vicinity of shroud entry). Gas injection into shroud tends to exert influence on tundish hydrodynamics⁹⁾ and this in turn, can affect different flow volumes in the tundish. To investigate the role of gas injection into ladle shroud and its attendant influence on tundish hydrodynamics and RTD phenomena, a transient, turbulent, two-phase VOF calculation procedure has been developed. For the sake of simplicity, slag-less, isothermal calculations have been carried out in which, a volumetric argon injection rate, corrected to a mean liquid temperature of 1873 K and 1at. pressure was embodied (e.g., Table 1). Governing equations of flow, turbulence, volume advection and scalar transport applicable to tundish flow modelling together with the associated boundary conditions have been discussed in many text books and publications (for example, see ref. 8) and these are consequently, not reproduced here.

Figure 8 Predicted mixture velocity field along (a) a transverse vertical plane passing through the inlet and the central strand and (b) a longitudinal vertical plane passing through the outlets.

Gas-liquid mixture velocity in the industrial scale, modified design tundish (Case IV) is shown in Fig.8. This exhibits features comparable to the single phase, flow modeling results presented earlier in Fig. 7. While typical magnitude of average speed of liquid recirculation throughout the domain is comparable, penetration of the incoming liquid jet, as seen, is significantly reduced in the presence of argon injection. This is to be expected and is due to the influence of the surfacing, argon+steel, buoyant plume on bulk melt flow. Gas injection in shroud thus tends to retard melt flow and produces more diffused, uniform liquid flows towards tundish outlets (compare, for example, Figs. 7 and 8). Resultant influence on tracer dispersion phenomena is readily apparent from the corresponding RTD curves and

the estimates of dispersed plug flow volume fractions shown in Fig. 9 and Table 4 respectively. Interestingly, dispersed plug flow volume in the tundish with argon injection in ladle shroud is significantly higher than one without argon injection (0.196 vs. 0.11).

Figure 9 Predicted C curves in the industrial scale tundish (Case IV) with and without argon injection in ladle shroud.

Table 4 Predicted RTD parameters in the industrial scale tundish with and without argon injection in shroud.

Tundish design	Phases	Time, s		Residence time, s		Volume fractions		
		Min	Peak	average	Nominal	Dead	Dispersed	Mixed
Case IV	Steel	88	420	1031.3	1295.3	0.20	0.19	0.60
	Steel + argon	57	229	935.1	1295.3	0.28	0.11	0.61

Water modelling results, numerical simulations and full-scale predictions presented so far, appear to confirm collectively consistent impact of flow modifiers on tundish hydrodynamic performance. These further suggest that incorporating a basal wedge, a pouring box and a twin slotted dam, proportion of dispersed plug volume can be significantly increased helping produce relatively clean steel from the bloom casting tundish. To explore and demonstrate this further, plant scale trials with original and modified design tundish were carried out in a 150,000TPA, special steel mill.

Figure 10 Different states of the three-strand, bloom casting tundish. (a) a new prepared tundish (b) a new tundish with stopper rod and tundish cover and (c) Operation with a new three strand tundish.

2.3. Industrial Scale Measurements and Validation of Water Modelling and Full-scale Computational Results

Interior designs of two different tundishes were modified in the plant by integrating a basal wedge in conjunction with a pouring box and a slotted dam, taking all precautions into account. Modified tundishes thus prepared were pre-heated and made ready for deployment in continuous casting operation. Casting was carried out and terminated following routine procedures. Plant trials have indicated that modified design tundish allows smooth casting on a sustained basis and facilitates easy de-skulling.

Steel samples collected from cast blooms were prepared, polished and subjected to microscopic analysis. Well established sample preparation norms were followed and samples thus prepared were analysed under both optical (OM) and scanning electron (SEM) microscopes. During OM observation, images were taken at various magnifications and a number of lower magnification images were further analyzed to obtain the volume fraction, size and size distributions of inclusions. Images were processed and analyzed via the commercial image analysis software AxioVision™ by Carl Zeiss GmbH. In addition, higher magnification SEM images together with EDS analysis were used to determine the composition of the inclusions present in steel samples.

Figure 11 (a) Optical image of a polished steel Sample and (b) SEM-EDS image of the same polished-etched steel sample.

In all samples, inclusions were found to be predominantly of deoxidation origin, containing oxides (alumina), silicates (alumino-silicate) and sulphides (manganese sulphide), having a wide size range (2 to 70 μm). Exogenous inclusions were rarely seen in the steel samples. Furthermore, formation of such small inclusions due to re-oxidation can also be safely ruled out. Typical optical and SEM-EDS images of a sample are shown in Fig.11. The SEM EDS image suggests presence of a 20 μm size alumina inclusion. Several sites were probed to identify the types of inclusions present in any given sample. Altogether twenty samples of identical grades of steel were investigated; ten each from blooms produced via the original and modified design tundishes, through a standardized, EAF-LF-VD-CC processing route. A summary of the findings is presented in Table 5. This reveals a systematic trend suggesting essentially that mean inclusion size and volume fractions are reduced in blooms cast

through the modified design tundish. Evidently, higher dispersed plug flow volume and surface directed flows help produce clean steel.

Table 5 Volume fraction, size distribution and average inclusion size in cast bloom samples of same grade of steel obtained from four different heats.

Original tundish design (Case I)			Modified tundish design (Case IV)		
Sample No.	Volume (%)	Size range and average size (μm)	Sample No.	Volume (%)	Size range and average size (μm)
1	7.4 \pm 3	2-10 (6.5)	1	1.2 \pm 1	3.0-9.0 (6.2)
2	5.6 \pm 2	2-9 (3.5)	2	11.2 \pm 2.4	3.4-7.0 (4.8)
3	8.5 \pm 1.5	2-15 (8)	3	4.2 \pm 2	1.8-7.1 (3.7)
4	20 \pm 4	5-25 (8.5)	4	5.9 \pm 1.5	2.3-8.3 (5.5)
5	25 \pm 2.5	5-40 (12.5)	5	2.7 \pm 1.5	2.1-5.5 (2.9)
6	24 \pm 5	5-70 (15)	6	2.2 \pm 1	2.9-11.4 (5.0)
7	6 \pm 3	2-15 (4.5)	7	31.9 \pm 3.5	2.7-5.8 (4.5)
8	42 \pm 3	5-30 (7.5)	8	25.8 \pm 4	2.8-12.3 (10.0)
9	9 \pm 1.5	2-10 (4.5)	9	2.2 \pm 1.6	1.3-12.5 (8.8)
10	5.6 \pm 2	2-20 (8)	10	23.8 \pm 2.5	4.1-14.1 (7.9)

3. CONCLUSIONS

Incorporating appropriate flow modifiers or flow control devices (FCD) in a three strand, delta shaped tundish, proportion of dispersed plug flow volume has been increased. To this end, gas injection in ladle shroud is beneficial and can further increase dispersed plug flow volume than is possible through flow modifiers alone. Industrial scale trials confirm that increased dispersed plug flow volume is conducive to inclusion floatation and help produce clean steel.

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